

THE FISCHER-CLIFORD MATRICES AND CHARACTER TABLE OF THE GROUP $2^6:A_7$

Rauhi I. Elkhatib

Dept. of Mathematics, Faculty of Applied Science,
Thamar University, Yemen

ABSTRACT

The split extension alternating group $2^6:A_7$ of order 161280 with index 28431 is a maximal subgroup of the orthogonal group $O(7,3)$ of order $4585351680 = 2^9 \cdot 3^9 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 13$. This Group has four inertia factor groups namely, A_7 , A_6 , S_5 and $(C_3 \times A_4):C_2$ of indices 1, 7, 21 and 35 respectively in A_7 . The aim of this paper is to construct the Fischer-Clifford matrices of $2^6:A_7$, which together with the associated partial character tables of the inertia groups, are used to compute the full character table of \bar{G} . There are 9 Fischer-Clifford matrices with sizes between 1×1 and 6×6 .

Mathematics Subject Classification: 20G15, 20C40.

Keywords: Linear Groups, Group Extensions, Character Table, Clifford Theory, Inertia Groups, Fischer-Clifford Matrix.

I. INTRODUCTION

The theory of Clifford-Fischer matrices, which is based on Clifford Theory (see [1]) Was developed by B. Fischer (see [2]). Let $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$ be the split extension of $N = 2^6$ by $G = A_7$ where N is the vector space of dimension 6 over $GF(2)$ on which G acts naturally. The aim of this paper is to construct the character table of \bar{G} by using the technique of Fischer-Clifford matrix $M(g)$ for each class representative g of G and the character tables of the inertia factor groups H_i of the inertia groups $\bar{H}_i = 2^6:H_i$. we use the properties of the Fischer-Clifford matrices discussed in ([3], [4], [5], [9], [12]) to compute entries of these matrices.

The Fischer-Clifford matrix $M(g)$ will be portioned row-wise into blocks, where each block corresponds to an inertia group \bar{H}_i . Now using the columns of character table of the inertia factor H_i of \bar{H}_i which correspond to classes of H_i which fuse to the class $[g]$ in G and multiply these columns by the rows of the Fischer-Clifford matrix $M(g)$ that correspond to \bar{H}_i . Thus, we construct the portion of the character table of \bar{G} which is in the block corresponding to \bar{H}_i for the

classes of \bar{G} that come from the coset $N\bar{g}$. For more information about this technique see ([3], [4], [5], [9], [12]).

The character table of \bar{G} will be divided row-wise into blocks where each block corresponding to an inertia group $\bar{H}_i = N:H_i$. The computations have been carried out with the aid of Maple [6], computer algebra system MAGMA [11] and GAP [10], Finally we will follow the notion of Atlas [8].

II. THEORY OF FISCHER-CLIFFORD MATRICES

Let $\bar{G} = N:G$ be a split extension of N by G . Then for $\theta \in Irr(N)$, we define $\bar{H} = \{x \in \bar{G} : \theta^x = \theta\} = I_{\bar{G}}(\theta)$ and $H = \{x \in G : \theta^x = \theta\} = I_G(\theta)$ where $I_{\bar{G}}(\theta)$ is the stabilizer of θ in the action of \bar{G} on $Irr(N)$, we have that $I_{\bar{G}}(\theta)$ is a subgroup of \bar{G} and N is normal subgroup in $I_{\bar{G}}(\theta)$. Also $[\bar{G}:I_{\bar{G}}(\theta)]$ is the size of the orbit containing θ . Then it can be shown that $\bar{H} = N:H$, where \bar{H} is the inertia group of θ in \bar{G} . The inertia factor $\bar{H}/N \cong H$ can be regarded as the inertia group of θ in the factor group $\bar{G}/N \cong G$. Define θ^g by $\theta^g(n) = \theta(gng^{-1})$ for $g \in \bar{G}, n \in N, \theta^g \in Irr(N)$. We say that θ is extendible to \bar{H} if there exists $\varphi \in Irr(\bar{H})$ such that $\varphi \downarrow_N = \theta$.

If θ is extendible to \bar{H} , then by Gallagher [7], we have $\{\alpha : \alpha \in Irr(\bar{H}), \langle \alpha \downarrow_N, \theta \rangle \neq 0\} = \{\beta\varphi : \beta \in Irr(\bar{H}/N)\}$. Let \bar{G} has the property that every irreducible character of N can be extended to its inertia group. Now let $\theta_1 = 1_N, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_t$ be representatives of the orbits of \bar{G} on $Irr(N)$, $\bar{H}_i = I_{\bar{G}}(\theta_i), 1 \leq i \leq t, \varphi_i \in Irr(\bar{H}_i)$ be an extension of θ_i to \bar{H}_i and $\beta \in Irr(\bar{H}_i)$ such that $N \subseteq Ker(\beta)$. Then it can be shown that

$$Irr(\bar{G}) = \bigcup_{i=1}^t \{(\beta\varphi_i)^G : \beta \in Irr(\bar{H}_i), N \subseteq Ker(\beta)\} = \bigcup_{i=1}^t \{(\beta\varphi_i)^G : \beta \in (\bar{H}_i/N)\}$$

Hence the irreducible characters of \bar{G} will be divided into blocks, where each block corresponds to an inertia group \bar{H}_i .

Let \bar{H}_i be the inertia factor group and φ_i be an extension of θ_i to \bar{H}_i . Take $\theta_1 = 1_N$ as the identity character of N , then $\bar{H}_1 = \bar{G}$ and $H_1 \cong G$. Let $X(g) = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{c(g)}\}$ be a set of representatives of the conjugacy classes of \bar{G} from the coset $N\bar{g}$ whose images under the natural homomorphism $\bar{G} \rightarrow G$ are in $[g]$ and we take $x_1 = \bar{g}$. We define $R(g) = \{(i, y_k) : 1 \leq i \leq t, H_i \cap [g] \neq \emptyset, 1 \leq k \leq r\}$

and we note that y_k runs over representatives of the conjugacy classes of elements of H_i which fuse into $[g]$ in G . Then we define the Fischer-Clifford matrix $M(g)$ by $M(g) = \left(\alpha_{(i,y_k)}^j \right)$, where $\alpha_{(i,y_k)}^j = \sum_l^t \frac{|C_{\bar{G}}(x_j)|}{|C(y_{lk})|} \varphi_i(y_{lk})$ with columns indexed by $X(g)$ and rows indexed by $R(g)$ and where \sum_l^t is the summation over all l for which $y_{lk} \sim x_j$ in \bar{G} . Then the partial character table of \bar{G} on

the classes $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{c(g)}\}$ is given by $\begin{bmatrix} C_1(g)M_1(g) \\ C_2(g)M_2(g) \\ \vdots \\ C_t(g)M_t(g) \end{bmatrix}$ where the Fischer-Clifford matrix

$M(g) = \begin{bmatrix} M_1(g) \\ M_2(g) \\ \vdots \\ M_t(g) \end{bmatrix}$ is divided into blocks $M(g)$ with each block corresponding to an inertia group

\bar{H}_i and $C_i(g)$ is the partial character table of H_i consisting of the columns corresponding to the classes that fuse into $[g]$ in G .

We can also observe that the number of irreducible characters of \bar{G} is the sum of the number of irreducible characters of the inertia factors H_i 's. The group $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$ is a split extension with 2^6 abelian and therefore by Mackey's theorem (see [4] - Theorem 4.1.12), we have each irreducible character of 2^6 can be extended to its inertia group in \bar{G} . Hence by the above theoretical outline we can fully determine the character table of $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$.

III. THE CONJUGACY CLASSES OF $2^6:A_7$

In this section, we will use the method of coset analysis to determine the conjugacy classes of $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$. So, we will consider $G = A_7$ and $N = 2^6$. We refer the reader to ([3], [4], [5], [9], [12]) for full details and background material regarding the method of coset analysis. Most of the information, which involved the conjugacy classes and permutation characters, were obtained by using direct computations in GAP [10] and MAGMA [11].

By MAGMA [11], we generate G by the two 6×6 matrices:

$$a = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad b = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Thus, we constructed the conjugacy class representative of G in terms of 6×6 matrices over $GF(2)$ by GAP[10]. The group G has 9 conjugacy classes and under the action of G on N , we obtain four orbits of lengths 1, 7, 21 and 35. The point stabilizers for orbits of lengths 1, 7, 21 and 35 are the subgroups A_7, A_6, S_5 and $(C_3 \times A_4):2$ with indices 1, 7, 21 and 35, respectively in G .

Let $\mathcal{X}(G|N)$ be the permutation character of G on N . The values of $\mathcal{X}(G|N)$ on different classes of G determine the number of k of fixed points of each conjugacy class of G in N . These values of the k 's will help us to calculate the conjugacy classes of $2^6:A_7$ which are listed in Table 1. Consequentially, having obtained the values of the k 's for the various classes of G , we then need to calculate the values of f_i 's corresponding to the various k 's, where f_i 's are the number of orbits Q_i 's for $1 \leq i \leq k$, that fuse together under the action of $C_G(g)$ to form one orbit Δ_j . For this purpose, we used Programme A [4]. For a class representative $dg \in \bar{G}$, where $d \in N, g \in G$ and $o(g) = m$, by Theorem 3.3.10 in [12] we have

$$o(dg) = \begin{cases} m & \text{if } w = 1_N \\ 2m & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

To calculate the orders of the class representative $dg \in \bar{G}$, we used Programme B [4]. If $o(g) = m$ and $w = 1_N$ then $o(dg) = m$ otherwise if $w \neq 1_N$, then $o(dg) = 2m$. To each class of \bar{G} , we have attached some weight m_{ij} which will be used later in computing the Fischer matrices of the extension. These weights are computed by the formula

$$m_{ij} = [N_{\bar{G}}(N\bar{g}_i):C_{\bar{G}}(g_{ij})] = |N| \frac{|C_G(g_i)|}{|C_G(g_{ij})|}$$

Thus, we obtained 32 conjugacy classes for the group $2^6:A_7$ and we list these results about the conjugacy classes of \bar{G} in Table 1.

Table (1): Conjugacy Classes of \bar{G}

$g_i \in G$	k_i	f_i	$m_{i,j}$	$[x]_{\bar{G}}$	$ [x]_{\bar{G}} $	$ C_{\bar{G}}(x) $
$g_1 = 1a$	64	1	1	$g_{1,1} = 1a$	1	161280
		7	7	$g_{1,2} = 2a$	7	23040
		21	21	$g_{1,3} = 2b$	21	7680
		35	35	$g_{1,4} = 2c$	35	4608
$g_2 = 2a$	16	1	4	$g_{2,1} = 2d$	420	384
		1	4	$g_{2,2} = 4a$	420	384
		2	8	$g_{2,3} = 4b$	840	192
		3	12	$g_{2,4} = 2e$	1260	128
		3	12		1260	128

		6	24	$g_{2,5} = 4c$ $g_{2,6} = 4d$	2520	64
$g_3 = 4a$	4	1	16	$g_{3,1} = 4e$	10080	16
		1	16	$g_{3,2} = 4f$	10080	16
		1	16	$g_{3,3} = 8a$	10080	16
		1	16	$g_{3,4} = 8b$	10080	16
$g_4 = 3a$	4	1	16	$g_{4,1} = 3a$	4480	36
		1	16	$g_{4,2} = 6a$	4480	36
		1	16	$g_{4,3} = 6b$	4480	36
		1	16	$g_{4,4} = 6c$	4480	36
$g_5 = 3b$	16	1	4	$g_{5,1} = 3b$	280	576
		1	4	$g_{5,2} = 6d$	280	576
		4	16	$g_{5,3} = 6e$	1120	144
		4	16	$g_{5,4} = 6f$	1120	144
		6	24	$g_{5,5} = 6g$	1680	96
$g_6 = 6a$	4	1	16	$g_{6,1} = 6h$	3360	48
		1	16	$g_{6,2} = 12a$	3360	48
		2	32	$g_{6,3} = 12b$	6720	96
$g_7 = 5a$	4	1	16	$g_{7,1} = 5a$	8064	20
		1	16	$g_{7,2} = 10a$	8064	20
		1	16	$g_{7,3} = 10b$	8064	20
		1	16	$g_{7,4} = 10c$	8064	20
$g_8 = 7a$	1	1	64	$g_{8,1} = 7a$	23040	7
$g_9 = 7b$	1	1	64	$g_{9,1} = 7b$	23040	7

Thus, the group $2^6:A_7$ has 32 conjugacy classes.

IV. THE INERTIA FACTOR GROUP OF $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$

The action of G on N produce four orbits of lengths 1, 7, 21 and 35. Hence by Brauer's theorem (see Theorem 5.1.4 in [12]) G acts on $\text{Irr}(N)$ with the same number of orbits. The lengths of these orbits will be $1, r, s$ where $1 + r + s = 64$, with corresponding point stabilizers H_1, H_2 , and H_3 as subgroups of G such that $[G:H_1] = 1, [G:H_2] = 7, [G:H_3] = 21$ and $[G:H_4] = 35$.

Considering the indices of these subgroups in G and investigating the maximal and submaximal subgroups of G , we have the Group A_7 acting on $\text{Irr}(2^6)$ produce four inertia factor groups:

- (1) $H_1 = A_7$ of index equal 1,
- (2) $H_2 = A_6$ of index equal 7,
- (3) $H_3 = S_5$ of index equal 21,
- (4) $H_4 = (C_3 \times A_4):C_2$ of index equal to 35.

Using GAP [10], we can generate the group $H_2 = A_6$ in terms of 6×6 matrices over GF(2) by the follows matrices:

$$a_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, a_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, a_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

By using these generators in GAP [10], we obtained the conjugacy classes and the character tables for this group.

We can complete the fusion maps by using matrix conjugation in the group A_7 . This fusion map is listed in table 2.

Table 2: The Fusion of the group $H_2 = A_6$ into the group $G = A_7$

$[g]_{H_2} \Rightarrow$	$[g]_G$	$[g]_{H_2} \Rightarrow$	$[g]_G$	$[g]_{H_2} \Rightarrow$	$[g]_G$
1a \Rightarrow	1a	5a \Rightarrow	5a	3a \Rightarrow	3a
5b \Rightarrow	5a	4a \Rightarrow	4a	3b \Rightarrow	3b
2a \Rightarrow	2a				

Also, by using GAP [10], we can generate the group $H_3 = S_5$ in terms of 6×6 matrices over GF(2) by the follows matrices:

$$b_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, b_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, b_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

By using these generators in GAP [10], we obtained the conjugacy classes and the character tables for this group.

We can complete the fusion maps by using matrix conjugation in the group A_7 . This fusion map is listed in table 3.

Table 3: The Fusion of the group $H_3 = S_5$ into the group $G = A_7$

$[g]_{H_3} \Rightarrow$	$[g]_G$	$[g]_{H_3} \Rightarrow$	$[g]_G$	$[g]_{H_3} \Rightarrow$	$[g]_G$
1a \Rightarrow	1a	6a \Rightarrow	6a	4a \Rightarrow	4a
5a \Rightarrow	5a	2a \Rightarrow	2a	3a \Rightarrow	3b
2b \Rightarrow	2a				

Also, by using GAP [10], we can generate the group $H_4 = (C_3 \times A_4):C_2$ in terms of 6×6 matrices over GF(2) by the follows matrices:

$$b_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, b_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, b_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

By using these generators in GAP [10], we obtained the conjugacy classes and the character tables for this group.

We can complete the fusion maps by using matrix conjugation in the group A_7 . This fusion map is listed in table 4.

Table 4: The Fusion of the group $H_4 = (C_3 \times A_4):C_2$ into the group $G = A_7$

$[g]_{H_3} \Rightarrow$	$[g]_G$	$[g]_{H_3} \Rightarrow$	$[g]_G$	$[g]_{H_3} \Rightarrow$	$[g]_G$
1a \Rightarrow	1a	3a \Rightarrow	3a	3b \Rightarrow	3a
3c \Rightarrow	3b	4a \Rightarrow	4a	6a \Rightarrow	6a
2a \Rightarrow	2a	3d \Rightarrow	3b	2d \Rightarrow	2a

V. The Fischer-Clifford Matrices of $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$

For each conjugacy class $[g]$ of G with representative $g \in G$, we construct the corresponding Fischer-Clifford matrix $M(g)$ of $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$. We use the properties of the Fischer-Clifford matrices (see ([3], [4], [5], [9], [12]) together with fusions of H_2 into H_1 , H_3 into H_1 and H_4 into H_1 (Table 2, Table 2, Table 4) to compute the entries of these matrices and to construct an algebraic system of linear and non-linear equations with the help of the Maple [6], we can solve these system of equations and compute all the Fischer matrices of \bar{G} .

The Fischer-Clifford matrix will be partitioned row-wise into blocks, where each block corresponding to an inertia group \bar{H}_i . We list the Fischer-Clifford matrices of \bar{G} in Table 5:

Table 5: The Fischer-Clifford Matrices of $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$

$M(g)$	$M(g)$
$M(1a) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 7 & 7 & -1 & -1 \\ 21 & -3 & -5 & 3 \\ 35 & -5 & 5 & -3 \end{bmatrix}$	$M(2a) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 3 & -3 & -3 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 2 & -2 & 0 & 2 & -2 & 0 \\ 3 & -3 & 3 & -2 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 & 1 \\ 6 & 6 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -2 \end{bmatrix}$
$M(4a) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$M(3a) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$M(3b) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 4 & -4 & 2 & -2 & 0 \\ 6 & 6 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & -4 & -2 & 2 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$M(6a) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 2 & -2 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$
$M(5a) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$M(7a) = [1]$
$M(7b) = [1]$	

VI. The Character Table of $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$

Now, we have:

- (1) The conjugacy classes of $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$ (Table 1);
- (2) The character tables of all the inertia factors (GAP [10]);
- (3) The fusions of conjugacy classes of the inertia factors into classes of A_7 (Tables 2, 3, 4);
- (4) The Fischer matrices of classes of $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$ (Table 5);

Thus, we can construct the character table of the $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$ as follows:

Table 6. The Character Table of $\bar{G} = 2^6:A_7$

Class	1a	2a	2b	2c	2d	2e	3a	3b	4a	4b	4c	4d
Order	1	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	4	4	4	4
Size	1	7	21	35	420	1260	4480	280	420	840	1260	2520
X1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
X2	6	6	6	6	2	2	0	3	2	2	2	2
X3	10	10	10	10	-2	-2	1	1	-2	-2	-2	-2
X4	10	10	10	10	-2	-2	1	1	-2	-2	-2	-2
X5	14	14	14	14	2	2	-1	2	2	2	2	2
X6	14	14	14	14	2	2	2	-1	2	2	2	2
X7	15	15	15	15	-1	-1	0	3	-1	-1	-1	-1
X8	21	21	21	21	1	1	0	-3	1	1	1	1
X9	35	35	35	35	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1
X10	7	7	-1	-1	3	0	1	4	-3	-3	2	0
X11	35	35	-5	-5	3	0	-1	8	-3	-3	2	0
X12	35	35	-5	-5	3	0	2	-4	-3	-3	2	0
X13	56	56	-8	-8	0	0	-1	-4	0	0	0	0
X14	56	56	-8	-8	0	0	-1	-4	0	0	0	0
X15	63	63	-9	-9	3	0	0	0	-3	-3	2	0
X16	70	70	-10	-10	-6	0	1	4	6	6	-4	0
X17	21	-3	-5	3	5	0	0	6	-5	3	-2	0
X18	21	-3	-5	3	1	-4	0	6	-1	3	2	0
X19	84	-12	-20	12	-4	-4	0	6	4	0	4	0
X20	84	-12	-20	12	4	4	0	6	-4	0	-4	0
X21	105	-15	-25	15	5	0	0	-6	-5	3	-2	0
X22	105	-15	-25	15	1	-4	0	-6	-1	3	2	0
X23	126	-18	-30	18	-6	4	0	0	6	-6	0	0
X24	35	-5	5	-3	7	-1	2	5	7	-1	-1	-1
X25	35	-5	5	-3	-5	-1	2	5	-5	-1	-1	3
X26	70	-10	10	-6	2	-2	-2	-2	2	-2	-2	2
X27	70	-10	10	-6	2	-2	-2	7	2	-2	-2	2
X28	70	-10	10	-6	2	-2	1	-5	2	-2	-2	2
X29	70	-10	10	-6	2	-2	1	-5	2	-2	-2	2
X30	105	-15	15	-9	-7	1	0	3	-7	1	1	1
X31	105	-15	15	-9	5	1	0	3	5	1	1	-3
X32	210	-30	30	-18	-2	2	0	-3	-2	2	2	-2

Class	4e	4f	5a	6a	6b	6c	6d	6e	6f	6g	6h
Order	4	4	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Size	10080	10080	8064	4480	4480	4480	280	1120	1120	1680	3360
X1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
X2	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	3	3	3	-1
X3	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
X4	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
X5	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	2	2	2	2	2
X6	0	0	-1	2	2	2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1
X7	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	3	3	3	3	-1
X8	-1	-1	1	0	0	0	-3	-3	-3	-3	1
X9	1	1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1
X10	1	1	2	1	-1	-1	-4	2	-2	0	0
X11	-1	-1	0	-1	1	1	-8	4	-4	0	0
X12	-1	-1	0	2	-2	-2	4	-2	2	0	0
X13	0	0	1	-1	1	1	4	-2	2	0	0

X14	0	0	1	-1	1	1	4	-2	2	0	0
X15	1	1	-2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
X16	0	0	0	1	-1	-1	-4	2	-2	0	0
X17	1	-1	1	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	2
X18	-1	1	1	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	-2
X19	0	0	-1	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	2
X20	0	0	-1	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	-2
X21	-1	1	0	0	0	0	-6	0	0	0	2
X22	1	-1	0	0	0	0	-6	0	0	0	-2
X23	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
X24	1	-1	0	-2	0	0	-3	-3	1	1	1
X25	-1	1	0	-2	0	0	-3	-3	1	1	1
X26	0	0	0	2	0	0	6	0	-4	2	2
X27	0	0	0	2	0	0	-9	-3	5	-1	-1
X28	0	0	0	-1	-3	3	3	3	-1	-1	-1
X29	0	0	0	-1	3	-3	3	3	-1	-1	-1
X30	1	-1	0	0	0	0	3	-3	-3	3	-1
X31	-1	1	0	0	0	0	3	-3	-3	3	-1
X32	0	0	0	0	0	0	-3	3	3	-3	1

Class	7a	7b	8a	8b	10a	10b	10c	12a	12b
Order	7	7	8	8	10	10	10	12	b
Size	23040	23040	10080	10080	8064	8064	8064	3360	6720
X1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
X2	-1	-1	0	0	1	1	1	-1	-1
X3	A	/A	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
X4	/A	A	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
X5	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	2	2
X6	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1
X7	1	1	-1	-1	0	0	0	-1	-1
X8	0	0	-1	-1	1	1	1	1	1
X9	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	-1	-1
X10	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	-2	0	0
X11	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
X12	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
X13	0	0	0	0	B	-B	-1	0	0
X14	0	0	0	0	-B	B	-1	0	0
X15	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	2	0	0
X16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
X17	0	0	1	-1	-1	-1	1	-2	0
X18	0	0	-1	1	-1	-1	1	2	0
X19	0	0	0	0	1	1	-1	-2	0
X20	0	0	0	0	1	1	-1	2	0
X21	0	0	-1	1	0	0	0	-2	0
X22	0	0	1	-1	0	0	0	2	0
X23	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	1	0	0
X24	0	0	-1	1	0	0	0	1	-1
X25	0	0	1	-1	0	0	0	1	-1
X26	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	-2
X27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	1
X28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	1
X29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	1
X30	0	0	-1	1	0	0	0	-1	1
X31	0	0	1	-1	0	0	0	-1	1
X32	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	-1

Explanation of Character Value Symbols:

$$A = \frac{-1 - \sqrt{-7}}{2}, \quad B = \sqrt{5}$$

REFERENCES

- A. H. Clifford, "Representations induced in an invariant subgroup" Ann. of Math. 38 , 1937, pp. 533 - 550.
- B. Fischer, "Clifford matrices" Representation theory of finite groups and finite-dimensional Lie algebras, 1991, pp. 1 - 16.
- B. M. Basheer, "Clifford-Fischer Theory Applied to Certain Groups Associated with Symplectic Unitary and Thompson Groups" PhD Thesis, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Pietermaritzburg, 2012.
- F. Ali, "Fischer-Clifford Theory for Split and Non-Split Group Extensions" PhD Thesis, University of Natal, Pietermaritzburg, 2001.
- J. Moori, "On the Groups G^+ and G of the form $210:M22$ and $210:M22$ ", PhD Thesis, University of Birmingham, 1975.
- Maple 18, Technical Computing Software for Engineers.. Available: <http://www.maplesoft.com/downloads/SelectPlatform.aspx?hash=E0253A401AF2CB538C86F152F7EF11EC>.
- P. X. Gallagher, "Group characters and normal Hall subgroups", Nagoya Math. J. **21** (1962), pp. 223 - 230.
- R. A. Wilson et al., "Atlas of finite group representations". Available: <http://brauer.maths.qmul.ac.uk/Atlas/v3>.
- T. T. Seretlo, "Fischer-Clifford Matrices and Character Tables of Certain Groups Associated with Simple Groups $O^+8(2)$, HS and Ly", PhD Thesis, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Pietermaritzburg, 2012.
- The GAP Group, GAP – Groups, Algorithms, and Programming, Version 4.8.6; 2016. Available: <http://www.gap-system.org>.
- W. Bosma and J. J. Cannon, "Handbook of Magma Functions", Department of Mathematics, University of Sydney, November 1994.
- Z. E. Mpono, "Fischer Clifford Theory and Character Tables of Group Extensions", PhD Thesis, University of Natal, Pietermaritzburg, 1998.